

Abstract: LEADER development programs have a primary objective of enhancing the quality of life. However, their evaluation has been limited due to the extensive time required for analysis. This report investigates the contribution of the LEADER approach to improving the quality of life through a thirty-year case study in the Alcarria Conquense region of Spain (1991–2021). Funding for projects focused on rural heritage, infrastructure, and essential services has played a pivotal role in creating conditions for a prosperous life in the region. Nonetheless, limitations have emerged, including deepening territorial imbalances, a heavy reliance on local government entities, and potential drawbacks to the innovation and management capacity of other economic and social actors. While LEADER offer a valuable tool for policymakers seeking to enhance rural communities' quality of life, further analysis is necessary to refine their implementation and maximize their overall impact.

Keywords: services for the population, enhancement of heritage, proximity services, depopulation, territorial approach, LEADER program, Spain

Resumen: Los programas de desarrollo LEADER tienen como objetivo primordial mejorar la calidad de vida. Sin embargo, su evaluación ha sido limitada debido al tiempo requerido para dicho proceso. Este informe investiga la contribución del enfoque LEADER a la mejora de la calidad de vida a través de un caso de estudio en la región de la Alcarria Conquense de España durante treinta años (1991–2021). La financiación de proyectos centrados en el patrimonio rural, las infraestructuras y los servicios esenciales han desempeñado un papel fundamental en la creación de condiciones para una vida próspera en la región. No obstante, han surgido limitaciones, como los desequilibrios territoriales, una fuerte dependencia de las entidades de gobierno local e inconvenientes en la innovación y gestión de otros agentes económicos y sociales. Aunque LEADER ofrece una valiosa herramienta a los responsables políticos que buscan mejorar la calidad de vida de las comunidades rurales, es necesario un análisis más profundo para perfeccionar su aplicación y maximizar su impacto global.

Keywords: servicios a la población, valorización del patrimonio, servicios de proximidad, despoblación, enfoque territorial, programa LEADER, España

Highlights

- LEADER actions enhance well-being, strengthen identity, and foster sustainable development.
 - Constant public resource allocation, slight increase in population services.
 - Main risks in implementing LEADER approach are territorial imbalances, dependence on local bodies, weakened innovation.
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1. Introduction

Quality of life is a construct, which involves multiple factors relating to the objective and subjective wellbeing of people. (Martínez Fernández et al., 2016). It has evolved from the first materialistic formulations, focused on physical and economic wellbeing, to more comprehensive conceptions that incorporate subjective and contextual elements (Urzúa M & Caqueo-Urizar, 2012).

Although there is a lack of consensus regarding the meaning and specific components that make up quality of life, it can be said that this construct relates to the level of well-being and satisfaction of a person, considering the objective and subjective elements, as well as the value system and the spatial and temporal context in which they live (Ardila, 2003; Urzúa M & Caqueo-Urizar, 2012).

Quality of life is, at the same time, a theme rooted in the programs and policies of the European Union.

Recently, the European Commission has incorporated it as part of the common objectives established in its long-term vision for rural areas in the European Union (European Commission, 2021). Likewise, the European Spatial Planning Observation Network (ESPON) has incorporated this concept as one of its key themes and has even developed a methodology for its measurement (Stilling, 2022).

One of the most debated aspects in the academic literature on quality of life relates to the appropriate methods for its measurement. The main challenges include: the diverse and multi-faceted nature of the construct; its dynamic and contextual character; the lack of data; the interaction between the dimensions that form (Bowling, 2003; "World Health Organization Quality of Life Assessment ..." 1995).

One of the most recurrent criticisms of measurement methods is the lack of consideration of the territorial dimension (Martínez Fernández et al., 2016). This is especially true for indices that compare countries or regions, such as the Human Development Index (United Nations, 2022) or the Better Life Index (OECD, 2020) but also for the diverse surveys on quality of life that are available. The European Quality of Life Survey (Eurofound, 2017), for instance, despite considering certain spatial typologies does not cover the whole diversity of configurations present in the territory.

From a planning perspective, the relationship between territory and quality of life is essential. Territory has a direct impact on the individual and collective well-being of its inhabitant: the way in which the territory is planned and managed can influence accessibility to services and resources, environmental quality, security, and social cohesion, among other factors that affect people's quality of life. In this sense, territorial planning must take quality of life into account as a central variable in the definition of development goals and strategies.

2. LEADER Approach

In the early 1990s, the LEADER (Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale) Community Initiative was launched in Europe, as part of the Common Agricultural Policy. This programme, explicitly designed to boost the development of disadvantaged rural areas and had three programming stages: LEADER I (1991–1993); LEADER II (1994–1999) and LEADER+ (2000–2006). With the idea of increasing the coverage of LEADER and benefiting more territories, certain countries implemented their own development programmes.

On completion of the three programming periods, the European Commission considered that the LEADER Community Initiative had reached a level of maturity that enabled competent authorities of Member States and Local Action Groups (LAGs) to implement it (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2012). Consequently, the basic principles of the LEADER approach were included in regional and/or national rural development programmes and became a specific axis of rural development policy. This was the case in Spain, which implemented the Operational Programmes for Development and Economic Diversification in Rural Areas: PRODER I (1996–1999) and PRODER II (2000–2006), both of which replicated LEADER principles and methodology. From 2007, the LEADER programmes were integrated into regional and/or national rural development programmes: in the Spanish context Axis 4 (2007–2013) and Measure 19 (2014–2020).

Over the years, LEADER approach have undergone modifications but the essential principles have been maintained: a) implementation on local, homogeneous and socially-united territories; (b) mobilisation of a bottom-up approach; (c) creation of partnerships called Local Action Groups (LAGs), made up of public and private partners operating across the territory, and are responsible for the local development strategies, and are set up as articulating bodies between local actors and regional, national and supranational (Cazorla Montero et al., 2005); (d) facilitation of innovation; (d) integrated and multi-sectoral interventions; (e) creation of networks; and (f) inter-territorial and transnational cooperation (European Commission, 2006).

In Poland, for example, Wojewódzka-Wiewiórska (2017) states that thanks to LEADER, it was possible to improve infrastructure and service provision to residents who had been marginalized or neglected in previous development policies. It is highlighted, for this same case, the important role that LEADER played

in building social capital (Chmieliński, 2011) and in meeting social needs in terms of leisure and free time. Something similar is reported for Germany, where the quality of life measurement records the highest scores for the dimensions "conditions in places of residence" and "personal activities", highlighting measures related to services to the population and the improvement of the rural environment and heritage as having the greatest impact on well-being (Moser et al., 2018).

Although quality of life has been an explicit policy goal for several decades now, defining and measuring it remains a challenge. (Costanza et al., 2008). For some authors, the link between heritage enhancement and quality of life is not sufficiently clear. It is argued, at least in the Spanish case, that the investments approved by Local Action Groups in this specific measure tend to favour urban actors more than rural ones and that in many cases, they do not even represent a source of income (García et al., 2005). On the other hand, some argue that, given the subjective nature of quality of life, the effects of these actions on the self-esteem and the strengthening of the identity of local inhabitants should be considered (Cejudo García & Maroto Martos, 2007). From these positions, economic aspects constitute only one of the dimensions of well-being.

All these studies affirm that the improvement of quality of life is an objective that is only partially achieved and that is presented in a differentiated manner in each territory (Kovács Katona et al., 2006).

This paper aims to analyse, through a case study, the contribution of LEADER programmes to improvement of the quality of life in rural areas in Europe, focusing on improving of services, environment, and heritage. The case selected is the Alcarria Conquense region in Castilla La Mancha, Spain, which joined the LEADER Community Initiative in 1991, and has gathered more than three decades of experience to date in the implementation of the territorial approach.

2.1 Analytical Framework

The European Commission developed the Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF) to assess the impact of rural development programmes, although, there is a great deal of criticism regarding its conceptualisation and application (EENRD, 2009), mainly due to the complexity of the measurement methodologies, the lack of data, the imprecision of the proposed definitions and the lack of articulation with the measures established in each of the programmes (Sancho Comíns & Reinoso Moreno, 2013).

In the case of quality of life, impact assessments are a challenge because of the multidimensional and to some extent intangible nature of the term, and because of the lack of consensus on the meaning of improvement of quality of life and the appropriate methods for its identification in the context of LEADER programmes.

In this regard, the Expert European Evaluation Network for Rural Development has developed an evaluation framework that considers the analysis of three basic dimensions of quality of life that affect the population: a) the socio-cultural and services dimension; b) the environmental dimension; and c) the economic dimension (Alfonso Fernandes et al., 2010).

Along the same lines, Sancho Comíns and Reinoso Moreno (2013) propose an evaluation framework that includes indicators that respond to the characteristics and specificities of the LEADER approach. The literature proposes nine impact categories, distributed in three areas (economy, quality of life and governance), assigning to each of them a series of indicators (means, implementation, outcome and impact) and evaluation criteria.

Given that quality of life is a subjective and intricate concept that proves challenging to quantify, relying on indicator-based analysis can furnish a robust and objective foundation for evaluating the impact of investments and enhancing decision-making processes for the welfare of rural communities.

In rural settings, "proximity services" denote indispensable facilities situated close to rural communities, addressing local needs. These services encompass grocery stores, medical centres, schools, gas stations, and other fundamental amenities integral to the daily lives of rural residents. The presence of these proximity services is crucial for safeguarding the well-being and health of the population, thereby enhancing the overall quality of life, and ensuring the sustainability of rural communities. Additionally,

access to such services is a vital prerequisite for fostering economic development, particularly in the context of depopulation prevalent in rural regions across Europe (Alloza et al., 2021). Restricted or limited access to basic services, coupled with a lack of economic and social opportunities, reduce a territory's capacity to retain its population and can lead to the intensification of migration flows to urban areas (Escalona & Díez, 2005; Ruiz Pulpón & Martínez Sánchez-Mateos, 2022).

Moreover, the protection and enhancement of rural environment and heritage, which refers to the set of tangible and intangible assets that bear witness to the ideational culture and way of life of inhabitants of rural areas (Hermosilla Pla & Iranzo García, 2004), are presented as resources with great potential to improve the quality of life in rural environments, although this relationship has not always been so clear or evident. The protection and enhancement of rural environment and heritage has been a key element of LEADER programmes since their inception.

This paper takes up the framework proposed by Sancho Comíns and Reinoso Martínez (2013) in order to answer the research questions based on a case study.

3. Case study

The choice of the Alcarria Conquense region as a case study is based on the following criteria: a) the territory has been a beneficiary of LEADER programmes since 1991, being one of the 52 territories in Spain that meet this requirement (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2012); b) the LAGs has 35 years' experience in the development of animation, training and awareness-raising activities in line with the principles of LEADER methodology Community Initiative (Díaz-Puente et al., 2011); and c) the territory has been recognised as an area of extreme depopulation by the General Government (2021/114405).

Fig 1. Territory of action of rural development programmes with the LEADER approach 1991–2021. Source: Gallego et al., 2021

⁵ Decree 108/2021 of 19 October determining the rural areas of Castilla-La Mancha, in accordance with the typology established in Article 11 of Law 2/2021 of 7 May on Economic, Social and Tax Measures to Combat Depopulation and Rural Development in Castilla-La Mancha. [2021/11440]

3.1 Institutional context

During the period between 1991 and 2021, three institutions have played a key role in the creation and management of LEADER programmes in the Alcarria Conquense region (see Figure 2). The first was the Community Development Institute (CDI of Cuenca) who contributed to the creation, in 1988, of ADINAC (the Association for the Comprehensive Development of the Alcarria Conquense) who have been selected in 1991 as the first LAG in the territory to manage a rural development programme within the framework of the LEADER Community Initiative (Díaz-Puente et al., 2014).

Fig 2. Origin and evolution of LAGs and Rural Development Programmes in the Alcarria Conquense region, 1991–2021. Source: Gallego et al., 2021.

In 1994, to make the LAG more representative of, and more deeply rooted in, the territory, ADINAC evolved from a legal entity made up of natural persons to a new entity made up of legal persons, both public and private, called CEDER Alcarria Conquense. CEDER Alcarria Conquense has been responsible for the management of four LEADER rural development programmes.

4. Methodology

To conduct this research, we opted for content analysis as our research technique, following the methodology proposed by (Berelson, 1952). This retrospective longitudinal analysis spans 30 years period, commencing in 1991 when the territory under scrutiny was designated as a beneficiary of the LEADER Community Initiative and concluding in 2021, marking the conclusion of the 2014–2020 programming period. The study unfolded in three successive stages, detailed as follows:

Stage 1. Analysis of the LEADER rural development programmes implemented in the Alcarria Conquense region: By synthesizing information extracted from the review of the identified technical documents (refer to Annex 1), we examined the indicators that were deemed most consequential for contextualizing the programs. These included the volume of public and private investments, the count of implemented projects, the number of beneficiaries, and the employment generated and sustained.

Stage 2. Identification of fundable measures and their relation to the area of quality of life: This phase aimed to identify the fundable measures that garnered support within each rural development program and wielded the most significant impact on enhancing the quality of life. This impact was assessed through two categories: a) services to the population and, b) rural environment and heritage.

These measures, exhibiting varying nature, objectives, and scope over the years, were stipulated in the regulatory framework of each program, shaping the program's implemented strategy. Analysing these measures necessitates a level of standardization and homogenization. To achieve this, the standardization approach outlined by Pillet and Plaza (2001) and expanded upon by Nieto and Gurría (2008) has been adopted to ensure consistency across different measures.

Stage 3. Analysis of the impact categories that contributed to the improvement of the quality of life: Drawing on the identification and categorization of eligible funding measures, we delved into the analysis of projects funded under each measure. Our focus was on discerning their contributions to impact

categories, specifically: a) services to the population and, b) rural environment and heritage. In this endeavour, we employed indicators developed by Sancho Comíns and Reinoso Moreno (2013) and scrutinized and deliberated on each impact category that played a role in enhancing the quality of life (see Table 1).

Tab 1. Indicators and measurement techniques for the analysis of quality-of-life impact categories. Source: Prepared by the authors based on data from (Sancho Comíns & Reinoso Moreno, 2013)

Impact categories	Indicators	Measuring technique
Services for the population	<p>Resource Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Total investment made</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Public investment</i> - <i>Private investment mobilised</i> <p>Implementation Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number and type of projects</i> ● <i>Number of centres and places created or renovated that serve the population</i> <p>Results Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Geographic coverage (No. of municipalities/total municipalities) and population coverage (No. of inhabitants/total inhabitants) with access to a service created or renovated by LEADER programmes.</i> 	<p>Documentary review</p> <p>Case Study</p>
Rural environment and heritage	<p>Resource Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Total investment made</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Public investment</i> - <i>Private investment mobilised</i> <p>Implementation Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number and type of rural heritage preservation and enhancement projects carried out</i> ● <i>Number and type of rural heritage preservation and enhancement projects at regional level</i> <p>Results Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Geographic coverage (No. of municipalities/total municipalities) and population coverage (No. of inhabitants/total inhabitants) of population centres where LEADER programmes have carried out projects for the renovation of rural settlements or heritage.</i> 	<p>Documentary review</p> <p>Case Study</p>

5. Results

5.1 Analysis of the LEADER rural development programs implemented in the Alcarria Conquense region

Between 1991 and 2021, we identified five rural development programs employing a LEADER approach. These programs can be delineated into three successive stages over the 30-year period. The initial phase, denoted as confirmation, is marked by the rural development initiatives spearheaded by the Association for the Integral Development of the Alcarria Conquense (ADINAC) since 1989. This stage is characterized by a specific territory, a strategic approach, and a regional partnership, forming the core of the LEADER Community Initiative. In this context, the territory became the beneficiary of its inaugural rural development program under the (1) LEADER Community Initiative spanning from 1991 to 1994. A subsequent phase, which we can identify as one of the expansion, is characterized by the implementation of the Operational Program for the Economic Diversification of Rural Areas (PRODER), a multiregional rural development program designed and implemented in Spain and co-financed by the European Union, with similar objectives to LEADER II, although with different management mechanisms: (2) PRODER (1997–1999) y (3) PRODER 2 (2000–2006). And the last stage, denoted as homogenization, the LEADER approach undergoes a transition from a Community Initiative to integration into the Rural Development Programs (RDP), specifically as a LEADER axis. Member States take on the responsibility of defining its strategic role within the rural development policy, aligning with

Community guidelines. Within this new framework, two distinct programs emerged: (4) Axis 4 of the Rural Development Program of Castilla-La Mancha (2007–2013) and (5) Measure 19 of the Rural Development Program of Castilla-La Mancha (2014–2020).

The execution of the five rural development programs utilizing the LEADER approach represents a comprehensive investment totalling €46,663,919 (see Table 2). More than half of this funding, specifically 54.6%, is sourced from public funds. Among these public funds, 73.67% is provided by the European Union, while the remaining 26.33% comes from national government entities. The remaining 45.4% of the total investment is contributed by private funds.

These financial resources facilitated the comprehensive implementation of 655 projects, with particular emphasis on the PRODER 2 program (2002–2006), boasting 165 executed projects. This program stands out due to a higher allocation of public investment across all programs and its integration into the territory of the natural region of Alcarria Conquense municipalities. In contrast, Program Measure 19 of the RDP of Castilla-La Mancha (2014–2020) experienced a distinct situation, recording the lowest number of funded projects, a total of 83. This was primarily attributed to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on investment flows and the unforeseen extension of the development program's execution by two years beyond the initial plan.

The projects identified were overseen by beneficiaries who received financial assistance from the development programs, thereby facilitating their investments. In total, 488 beneficiaries have been identified, including municipalities, SMEs, cooperatives, non-profit organizations, religious entities, foundations, and others.

All the investments undertaken have directly led to the establishment of 289 new jobs and the stabilization and enhancement of 260 existing positions. It's essential to underscore that the employment data, as generated by Program Axis 4 of the RDP of Castilla-La Mancha, mirror the adverse impacts of the economic crisis experienced in Spain between 2007 and 2012. The region of Alcarria Conquense did not escape this crisis, witnessing a 44% reduction in job creation between 2007 and 2013 compared to the average of other programs.

Tab 2. Rural development programs with the LEADER approach implemented in the Alcarria Conquense region 1991–2021.

FUNDING BY PROGRAMME (€)						
PROGRAMME	Public Funds	Private Funds	Total Investment	Total Projects	Total Beneficiaries	Total Employment
(1). LEADER Community Initiative (1991–1994)	3,048,970	2,459,895	5,508,865	125	104	118
(2). Programme for the Development and Economic Diversification of Rural Areas (1997–1999)	4,746,915	4,008,892	8,755,807	133	83	154
(3). Programme for the Development and Economic Diversification of Rural Areas (PRODER 2) (2000–2006)	7,337,424	8,358,035	15,695,459	165	99	110
(4). Axis 4 LEADER of Rural Development Programme of Castilla-La Mancha (2007–2013)	6,264,322	4,783,274	11,047,596	149	95	86
(5). Measure 19: Support for local development of LEADER of Rural Development Programme of Castilla-La Mancha (2014–2020)	4,082,361	1,573,832	5,656,193	83	107	81
TOTAL	25,479,992	21,183,928	46,663,919	655	488*	549

Source: prepared by the authors based on data obtained from the final reports of the rural development programs and the partial implementation reports of the Measure 19 Programme as of 30/04/2021. (*) Prominent entities have been recognized as beneficiaries across multiple programs, exemplified by the Local Action Group.

5.2 Identification of fundable measures and their relation to the area of quality of life

The exploration of fundable measures has offered a comprehensive perspective on the targeted investment areas during the analysed period. In the domain of enhancing the quality of life, it became evident that the five rural development programs incorporated fundable measures directed at improving the quality of life, categorizing them into two impact categories: a) services to the population and, b) rural environment and heritage (refer to Table 3). This classification allowed for the identification of distinct priorities and approaches within each program. As noted by Sancho Comíns and Reinoso Moreno (2013), these measures contribute significantly to the enhancement of the quality of life.

Tab 3. Relationship between fundable measures and the quality-of-life area of rural development programs 1991–2021. Source: prepared by the authors based on the framework by (Nieto Masot & Gurría Gascón, 2008; Pillet Capdepón & Plaza Tabasco, 2001)

	Impact category Fundable measures	Rural development programs with a LEADER focus				
		LEADER 1991–1995	PRODER 1997–1999	PRODER 2 2000–2006	Axis 4 2007–2013	Measure 19 2014–2020
Improvement of quality of life	Services for the population	3. Rural tourism*	2. Renewal and development of population centers not dominated by agricultural activity	103. Services for the population	321. Provision of basic services for the economy and the rural population 322. Renewal and development of rural communities	19.2.4. Financial aid for the creation, improvement, or extension of infrastructure in rural areas
	Rural environment and heritage	3. Rural tourism**	1. Enhancement of rural heritage	104. Natural heritage 107. Enhancement of cultural and architectural heritage.	323 Conservation and enhancement of rural heritage	19.2.5. Financial aid for the maintenance, recovery, and renovation of rural heritage

* Including sub-measures: 4.01 Creation of initiatives to provide basic services for municipalities and 4.02 Creation of small service enterprises

** Including sub-measures: 3.04. Renovation of architectural, popular, and historical heritage, 3.05 Creation of cultural and sports tourism and 3.06 Renovation of historical façades.

5.2.1 Services for the population

These measures have targeted the revitalization and advancement of rural communities, mitigated their decline, and enhanced their allure. They encompass the enhancement and establishment of fundamental services and infrastructure, crucial for economic development. These initiatives also strive to alleviate disparities between urban and rural areas, ultimately enhancing the quality of life for the rural population. Furthermore, these efforts aim to attract new residents while promoting the continued residence of the existing population.

5.2.2 Rural environment and heritage

The goals of these measures have been directed towards enhancing tourism potential and drawing visitors to rural areas through initiatives focused on conserving and revitalizing their heritage and landscape resources. Additionally, they aim to raise public awareness about the preservation and enhancement of these resources, coupled with actions dedicated to safeguarding and improving the natural environment.

In this context, it has been noted that the prioritization in the execution of rural development programs extends to various aspects, such as the initial allocation of funds based on specific measures and the approval dates of projects. Notably, there has been a focus on projects that not only support the elderly in remaining within the community but also enhance overall population access to new and improved services.

Tab 4. Resource, performance, and outcome indicators relating to services for the population. Source: prepared by the authors based on the review of rural development programs.

Indicator	LEADER 1991–1995	PRODER 1997–1999	PRODER 2 2000–2006	Axis 4 2007–2013	Measure 19 2014–2020
Resource indicator (€)					
Total investment	€548,064	1,045,654	1,072,510	1,127,159	2,073,117
Public investment	196,414	721,009	891,330	929,668	1,718,445
Private investment mobilised	351,650	324,645	181,180	197,491	354,672
Performance indicator					
Types of projects	10	16	23	18	36
Centers created or renovated	3	1	3	3	5
Places created or renovated	65	200	215	120	210
Outcome indicator					
Geographic coverage	6/25 24%	9/34 26%	17/42 40%	11/42 26%	18/43 41%
Population coverage	2,932/8,751 33.5%	5,297/10,314 51%	5,275/11,612 45%	4,109/10,565 38%	5,396/9,870 54%

This measure has led to the implementation of 103 projects, accounting for 15.7% of all projects implemented in the five rural development programmes. Of these projects, 15 have given rise to new centres such as sheltered homes, reading rooms and multi-purpose centres with a total of 810 places.

The typology of these projects (see Figure 3) has been categorized according to the expected impact on the improvement of the quality of life. This classification considers factors such as geographical coverage, the population's access to newly created or improved services, and the utilization of enhanced spaces and rehabilitated heritage by both local inhabitants and visitors.

- (1) Creation and improvement of basic services for the population. These projects have provided the territory with new infrastructures aimed at: i) offering new services to the population (17) and facilitating access to new technologies with Internet centres, transport within the region, and connections with the provincial capital using taxi service, giving older people the chance to stay in their village thanks to housing for the elderly, access to culture and participation by enabling reading rooms and multi-purpose centres and improved access to medical services through renovated consulting rooms; ii) improving the provision of green spaces and recreational areas (29) that facilitate outdoor activities for the elderly and young people and also constitute a tourist attraction; and iii) improving and expanding the offer of sports (7), especially in municipalities with a higher density of young people and where schools still exist.
- (2) Creation of infrastructures and services for local town councils. Several projects have been promoted by local town councils (11) to improve the quality of life of the population through the modernisation of public lighting to achieve greater energy efficiency; the provision of new machinery for street cleaning and plant waste treatment; the signposting of streets and unique buildings; and the provision of specialised machinery for municipal works and services.

- (3) Creation of infrastructures and adaptation of spaces focused on supporting rural tourism. The support and promotion of rural tourism has materialised in projects aimed at the creation of infrastructures (19) that contribute to the consolidation of the territory as a tourist destination. These projects include those aimed at signposting the territory, areas and buildings of tourist interest and routes and trails; interventions to enhance the value of emblematic architectural elements of the territory and those of a more strategic nature, such as inventories and studies; and those aimed at renovating public spaces (20) of special interest due to their history or architectural value that have contributed to the diversification of the tourist offer in the territory.

Fig 3. Types of projects relating to services for the population. Source: prepared by the authors based on the review of rural development programs

It should be noted that 97.3% of the projects have been promoted by local town councils. Geographic coverage has ranged from 24% in the implementation of the LEADER Initiative (1991–1995) to 41% in the Measure 19 LEADER Programme (2014–2020). The level of participation of local town councils has been conditioned by the level of co-financing that they had to assume in their projects – 20% of the total investment – which for most of the local town councils represents a very high investment effort. Proof of this is that the three municipalities with the largest population – they account for 41.1% of the total population of the territory – have been beneficiaries of 20.3% of the total investment of the measure and the local town council with the largest population of the territory – 1,716 inhabitants – has been the beneficiary of 9.2% of the total investment of the measure.

These data reveal two contrasting situations that have emerged in the implementation of rural development programs: the first refers to the obligatory nature of the regulations regarding the co-financing of a percentage of the investment for all local public entities without taking into account the socioeconomic diversity that the European Union itself establishes for rural territories: areas to be revitalized, intermediate and peri-urban areas, which clearly determine the investment capacity of local public entities.

The second arises from the Local Action Group's difficulty in instituting positive discrimination to support local public entities with limited investment capacity. This challenge is compounded by the generally restricted budgets that local public entities operate with, which are determined by the number of inhabitants they serve. Reducing the co-financing percentage for certain entities is not a feasible option, given the limitations faced by these entities and the resulting burden it would place on the remaining ones.

The implementation of the five rural development programmes in the territory has ensured that in all the municipalities, there is at least one improvement, renovation or creation of a service or space that has contributed to the improvement of the quality of life of their inhabitants. This highlights the technical and economic effort made by town councils such as Vindel with 11 inhabitants, Villarejo de la Peñuela

with 23 or Villar del Infantado with 45 inhabitants to be able to offer their neighbours a multi-purpose social centre, a meeting room or improved public lighting. The impact of these initiatives has been far-reaching, benefiting a wide spectrum of individuals. These improvements have encompassed various facets of community life, from establishing residences for the elderly and senior housing, to the creation of bio-healthy parks primarily designed for the elderly population. Additionally, they have led to the establishment of reading rooms and computer facilities that cater to individuals of all age groups. In this sense, these investments have been instrumental in revitalizing and modernizing crucial infrastructure elements within these towns.

Although the increase in service coverage is an indicator that by itself does not capture the complexity of quality of life, it is a key indicator that influences multiple aspects of the lives of individuals and communities.

5.2.3 Rural environment and heritage

Actions aimed at improving the rural environment and heritage have been part of the five rural development programmes implemented across the territory (see Table 5). In the first programme – LEADER – projects aimed at the recovery of rural heritage were included in the Rural Tourism measure, with the aim of not only improving the well-being of the population but also making visitors’ stay in the region more attractive.

For the period 1991–2021, an investment of €5,275,531 was made for the improvement of the rural environment and heritage, representing 11.3% of the total investment of all rural development programmes implemented in the region. The aid granted under the development programmes amounted to €3,908,226 and the contribution of the promoters or beneficiaries of the aid amounted to €1,367,305.

Tab 5. Resource, performance and outcome indicators relating to the rural environment and heritage. Source: prepared by the authors based on the review of rural development programmes.

Indicator	LEADER 1991–1995	PRODER 1997–1999	PRODER 2 2000–2006	Axis 4 2007–2013	Measure 19 2014–2020
Resource indicator (€)					
Total investment	1,011,021	860,519	1,381,037	1,182,024	840,930
Public investment	804,083	508,622	905,557	988,306	701,658
Private investment mobilised	206,938	351,897	475,480	193,718	139,272
Performance indicator					
Projects for the preservation and enhancement of rural heritage	15	27	37	48	14
Projects for the preservation and enhancement of regional heritage	2	2	3	0	1
Outcome indicator					
Geographic coverage	7/25 28%	15/34 44%	14/42 33%	30/42 71%	9/43 21%
Population coverage	2,748/8,751 31%	5,422/10,314 52%	2,978/11,612 25%	5,857/10,565 55%	2,168/9,870 22%

A total of 141 projects have been identified in this period, accounting for 22% of all projects implemented in the five rural development programmes. The typology of these projects (see Figure 4) has been categorised according to the expected impact on the improvement of quality of life: the use by local inhabitants or visitors of the improved spaces and the rehabilitated heritage.

- (1) Intervention in spaces and buildings. A number of projects have been carried out with the aim of improving and adapting public spaces of cultural interest (28) for the enjoyment of

the population. There have also been interventions in civil buildings (25) to provide them with a new use as social centres, Internet classrooms, libraries, etc.

- (2) Restoration of religious property and buildings. The restoration and recovery projects of movable heritage (13) together with the restoration of religious buildings (36) show the richness of the religious heritage of the region and the economic effort made over the last 30 years to enhance its value as one of the territory's most important resources.
- (3) Dissemination of the region's rural heritage. This section includes the projects carried out with the aim of providing the region with studies, inventories, and publications (8) that identify and catalogue the region's rich and diverse heritage. In addition, informative conferences (4) have been held to raise awareness among the population of the importance of the recovery and enhancement of rural heritage as a basis for other economic activities such as rural tourism.
- (4) Promotion of urban planning figures and of the territory's resources. With the completion of Archaeological Charters (14) and Forest Management Plans (13), all local town councils in the region have been provided with two planning documents required by the regional government to define the delimitations of land and forest use.

These projects have helped to promote knowledge, valorisation, restoration and enhancement of the territory's heritage and to turn it into a socioeconomic resource that has contributed to launching broad local economic sectors, creating employment and wealth, two of the keys that contribute to improving quality of life.

Fig 4. Types of projects relating to the rural environment and heritage. Source: prepared by the authors based on the review of rural development programs

Local town councils have been the main beneficiaries of this measure (see Figure 5), with more than 73% of the projects corresponding to initiatives implemented by these entities. The project goals have been related to the provision of urban planning tools and natural resources, as well as intervention in civil buildings and spaces of cultural interest for renovation, refitting and enhancement.

In this sense, the LAG has been the promoter of eight projects with a regional scope of action that will serve as an example for future interventions by Government bodies or private entities. These projects have focused on actions on archaeological heritage and natural spaces, as well as on the drawing up of inventories on the heritage and resources of the territory and the organisation of information and awareness-raising conferences.

In this measure, geographic coverage has ranged from 21% in the implementation of the Measure 19 (2014–2020) and 71% in the Axis 4 (2007–2013). In this respect, 75% of local town councils have been

promoters of between one and three projects and only 13% had not submitted any project at all. It is worth highlighting that the local town council with the largest population in the territory has implemented 12.6% of the total number of projects.

Over the thirty-year period (1991–2021), the coverage of the beneficiary population of the various projects under this measure has ranged from 55% in Axis 4 (2007–2013) to 22% in Measure 19 (2014–2020). Specifically, the Measure 19 witnessed a decline in the percentage of coverage due to the period of inactivity caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which persisted until 2021.

Fig 5. Number of projects and beneficiaries relating to the environment and heritage. Source: prepared by the authors based on the review of rural development programs

6. Discussion

One of the main consequences of the rural divide (Camarero & Oliva, 2019) is the increasing difficulty for rural localities to reach the quality of life standards prevailing in urban settings. In the context of LEADER Rural Development Programmes, quality of life has been assessed along two critical dimensions: access to basic services and improvement of the rural environment and heritage (Sancho Comíns & Reinoso Moreno, 2013). Both dimensions pose a challenge for economically depressed territories, which are experiencing dynamics of depopulation.

The lack of accessibility to services, both public and private, is one of the main expressions of the territorial inequality that affects rural populations. The lack of services adds to demographic, educational and employment problems, accelerating the deterioration of local conditions and deepening the gap between urban and rural areas (Camarero, 2020). For this reason, it is not surprising that since the first LEADER calls for proposals, action measures to improve services to the population have been foreseen.

The analysis of the projects financed over the last 30 years in the Alcarria Conquense region shows that the total investment aimed at improving or creating new services for the population has increased period after period, with the increases in PRODER (1997–1999) and Measure 19 (2014–2020) standing out above all. This trajectory is consistent with the positive evolution of resource, performance, and outcome indicators, which show the volumes of investment, the number of projects financed, the centres and places created or renovated, as well as the extension of the geographic coverage and the population benefited in each period.

A notable trend is the increasing significance of public investment as a proportion of total investment in projects serving the public, rising from 35.8% in the initial programming period to 82.8% in the most recent period under examination.

In the same vein, it should be underlined that, unlike other fundable measures, the promotion and implementation of projects has been almost entirely the responsibility of local town councils. While this situation is explained by the nature of the infrastructure and the activities involved in the provision of

services, the centrality exercised by local government bodies may represent a risk in terms of the effects that their technical and financial capacities have on the attraction of resources. In the Alcarria Conquense region, for example, the most populated municipalities, with the greatest capacity for co-financing and management, received the greatest number of resources and projects. Given the key role played by public and private services in economic development and the rooting of the population, it is foreseeable that this budget concentration process has contributed to widening the rural gap at the inter-regional level, thus deepening territorial imbalances.

Finally, it should be noted that a significant percentage of the projects that were financed as services for the population were aimed at consolidating the territory as a tourist destination. This link between quality of life and rural tourism has been present since the first LEADER programmes and, despite its good results, does have certain problematic aspects.

With regard to projects whose main goal was the enhancement of the rural environment and heritage, we can observe that, in general terms, investment amounts have remained stable over time, showing a slight decrease in PRODER (1997–1999) and Measure 19 (2014–2020).

In the analysis carried out, the periods corresponding to PRODER 2 (2000–2006) and Axis 4 (2007–2013) stood out as those in which public investment was highest and in which, therefore, the greatest number of projects were implemented. Likewise, these were also the periods in which the greatest geographic and population coverage was achieved. These results are in line with the growing importance of rural heritage in the successive calls for proposals for LEADER rural development programmes. However, it is important to highlight that in the last programming period (2014–2020) there was a drop in practically all the resource, performance and outcome indicators, making it the period with the worst performance. This situation is attributed to the entry into force of more restrictive legal rules for investments by local town councils, and to the suspension of administrative and implementation activities during the COVID-19 lockdown period.

As it was the case for public service projects, local town councils were the main beneficiaries of heritage enhancement measures. They were followed in importance by civil and religious bodies, and lastly by the LAGs, again showing the phenomenon of concentration of resources and projects in the most populated municipalities.

With regard to the type of projects financed, 72.3% corresponded to direct interventions on the material heritage (religious, civil or cultural) and the rest to the development of activities or the design of materials aimed at heritage management and dissemination.

The cultural and natural heritage, together with the physical infrastructure that enables access to services, are the most important resources of rural communities. They are the basis for the individual and collective identities of their inhabitants, thus constituting elements of cohesion and attachment to the territory (Carvalho, 2003). Furthermore, they can be seen as endogenous resources that have great potential to generate new economic alternatives and improve the living conditions of the population (Cejudo & Navarro, 2020).

In contexts of depopulation, access to services is conditioned not only by geographical factors but also by a series of economic aspects relating to the process of demographic decline, such as the fall in revenue levels, dependence on budgetary transfers and the increase in fixed costs per inhabitant (Alloza Frutos et al., 2021).

In the case analysed, despite the fact that the most isolated rural municipalities with the lowest population densities face the greatest difficulties in providing services for their inhabitants, investments directed towards this goal have centred on the most populated and connected municipalities, thus feeding back into the so-called “vicious circle of depopulation” (Wallace & Drudy, 1972). This phenomenon refers to the process by which the progressive decrease of the population affects the provision of infrastructure and services in a territory, deteriorating the economic conditions and the quality of life of the inhabitants, and therefore encouraging migration. This undesired effect must be addressed, as one of the explicit goals of LEADER development programmes is to promote territorial cohesion and balanced development of rural areas.

Meanwhile, the relationship between heritage and quality of life has been the subject of numerous studies, which highlight the role played by the recognition, renovation, preservation and enhancement of heritage in the revitalisation of cities or regions and in achieving inclusive and sustainable development (Carvalho, 2003; Cejudo et al., 2019; Moscoso, 2022). More specifically, the links between heritage, tourism and development are addressed, as well as the multiplier effects derived from the emergence of new economic activities (Mondéjar Jiménez et al., 2009; Páez Vives et al., 2022; Toselli, 2019; Viñals Blasco et al., 2017).

Although tourism can play an important role in the socio-economic dynamisation of the territory, its integration into heritage sites in rural areas is not free from contradictions (Troitiño Vinuesa & Troitiño Torralba, 2012). The high influx of visitors is a factor that, in addition to threatening the preservation of heritage assets, has a negative impact on the quality of life of the population (Cejudo & Maroto, 2007).

Certain authors suggest that among the actions that enable a better understanding of the relationship between heritage and quality of life are those relating to the maintenance, renovation and preservation of heritage assets that do not result in a direct economic benefit, beyond improving the appearance of the space in which they are located (Cejudo & Navarro, 2020; Molina & Ruiz-Valdepeñas, 2016). This is the case with the vast majority of the interventions that have been carried out in the Alcarria Conquense region, which have been aimed at the renovation and conditioning of the region's cultural, natural, public and, above all, religious heritage. In addition, it should be noted that a significant percentage of the projects carried out have been geared towards the creation of collections and instruments for management and decision-making at regional or local level, such as inventories, catalogues, studies, and land-use planning. Although the heritage enhancement associated with this type of project does not have a direct economic impact in the short term, it does have a positive impact on people's quality of life.

If we consider the wide geographic and population coverage that actions relating to the rural environment and heritage have had over three decades, it is possible to infer that their implementation, in the context of LEADER rural development programmes, has mainly contributed to the strengthening of the self-esteem and identity of local communities. This coincides with diagnoses made in other European territories (Carvalho, 2003; Cejudo & Maroto, 2007; Miranda & Moyano, 2020) which state that, given the limited amount of resources usually allocated to this measure, its socioeconomic impact has been more important in terms of identity than in economic terms.

7. Conclusions

An analysis of the contribution of LEADER programmes over thirty years shows that, in general terms, the resources allocated to these services for the population and rural environment and heritage remained constant over time, with slight increases in the case of services for the population, and a significant drop in the last period in the case of measures relating to the enhancement of the rural environment and heritage.

The high percentage of public investment in relation to total investment is quite striking in both types of measures, and so is the centrality of the local town councils as promoters and executors of the projects. While this is a foreseeable outcome because most of the actions relating to quality of life require, by their very nature, the convergence of the technical and managerial capacities that are present in public bodies, we must acknowledge the risks of concentrating functions on a single actor. This study identifies at least three: a) the deepening of territorial imbalances through the accumulation of resources and projects in the most populated and best-connected municipalities in the region; b) high dependence on local government bodies, and therefore greater vulnerability to external events; and c) potential weakening of the innovation and management capacity of other economic and social actors.

These undesired effects, associated with the implementation of the measures analysed, go against the principles of the LEADER approach and must be addressed in the design of rural development programmes. It would be desirable, in this sense, to establish compensatory measures that guarantee equity between territories and actors, in order to promote a comprehensive, sustainable development style, in line with local needs and resources. In rural territories, as exemplified in the case study,

the limited, and at times, non-existent technical capabilities, along with the scarce financial resources at the disposal of local entities, should not serve as justifications for denying the local population the benefits of planned investment measures. The proposal should be made within the regulatory framework governing rural development programs, in which financial and technical differentiation should be applied to the specific characteristics and needs of the territories that stand to benefit from these programs. Additionally, these efforts may encompass the promotion of strategic alliances among diverse local stakeholders and the implementation of adaptable approaches tailored to the characteristics of each territory. Local Action Groups (LAGs), in close collaboration with local communities, can assume a pivotal role in ameliorating these territorial disparities.

Although much of the literature refers to the potential for tourism that can be sparked by an adequate provision of public services, in the case analysed it can be seen that the actions that relate to this area, prioritise the creation and adaptation of infrastructures and public spaces. The same is true of actions aimed at the enhancement of the rural environment and heritage, which have been oriented towards the qualification of heritage assets that, regardless of their relevance for the tourism sector, have a direct impact on the well-being of the local population.

In this sense, we can say that both types of actions acquire their true dimension when, in addition to revitalising the economy of a territory, they strengthen the identity and sense of belonging of inhabitants, contributing directly or indirectly to their well-being.

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Annex 1 Documentation reviewed and analysed for the period 1991–2021.

Programme	Documents for analysis	Year
LEADER 1991–1994	Integrated Rural Development Programme for the Alcarria Conquense region within the framework of the LEADER Community Initiative.	1991
	Final Report	1995
	News archive	1995
	ADINAC Newsletter Collection Numbers 1–15	1991–1993
PRODER 1997–1999	Operational Programme for the Economic Diversification of Rural Areas	1996
	Report 1997–2001	2001
PRODER2 2000–2006	Territorial Development Programme 2000–2006	2000
	Report 2002–2006	2006
	Evaluation and Analysis of the Results of the Rural Development Programme of La Alcarria Conquense region. 2000–2006	2006
Axis 4 2007–2013	Territorial Programme for the Endogenous Development of La Alcarria Conquense region	2007
	Report 2007–2013	2013
Measure 19 2014–2020	Local Development Strategy for La Alcarria Conquense region	2016
	Projects selected, investments accepted, and subsidies granted in 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020	2021
20 years of Application of the LEADER Methodology in La Alcarria Conquense region 1991–2011		2011
30 years of Application of the LEADER Methodology in La Alcarria Conquense region 1991–2021		2021